

AFINET

AGROFORESTRY INNOVATION NETWORKS

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REPORT ON THE 3RD RAIN WORKSHOP IN PORTUGAL

Summary

The main objective of the meeting was to present, discuss and validate, by the portuguese RAIN members, the final list of innovations collected by the 9 RAINS of the AFINET project. It was also important to analyse the differences and similarities among european regions. These objectives were achieved trough the acomplishemnt of an oral presentation by ISA, followed by a discussion period from each one of the members presented in the meting.

The other objective was to use the opportunity created by this meeting to promote knowledge transfer about the carob tree. This native crop was chosen due to its characteristics and potential for dry climate conditions and its relevance for silvopastoral management systems.

At the end of the meeting the main conclusions to be referred are: i) the list of innovations is considered long and with large potential; ii) some RAIN members refereed the evidence of distinct groups of innovations from Northern/Central European countries versus the ones from Southern countries. This aspect did not raised an agreement among all of the present members; iii) the complementation of the meeting program with technical presentations and farmers testimonies, followed by a field visit, increases the visibility of the project and the participation of the RAIN members; iv) the place where the meeting takes place is crucial for the final list of attendance.

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Table of contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	II
LIST OF FIGURES	III
LIST OF TABLES.....	IV
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS.....	V
1. PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES.....	1
2. AGENDA OF THE 3 RD RAIN MEETING.....	2
3. LIST OF ATTENDEES	4
4. STAKEHOLDERS TAKING PART ON THE 3 RD RAIN MEETING.....	5
5. RESULTS OF THE 3 RD RAIN MEETING	6
5.1. <i>Validation list of innovations by stakeholders.....</i>	6
5.2. <i>Proposed AFINET synergy regions.....</i>	8
5.3. <i>Knowledge transfer during the 3^d RAIN.....</i>	9
6. CONCLUSIONS OF THE 3 RD RAIN.....	10
ANNEX I: LIST OF ATTENDEES.....	11

List of Figures

Figure 1. Proportion of each stakeholder category in the 3rd RAIN meeting in Portugal 5

List of Tables

Table 1. List of attendees of the 3 rd RAIN meeting in PORTUGAL	4
Table 2: Priority innovations for Portugal	7

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AFINET- Agroforestry Innovation Networks

RAIN – Regional Agroforestry Innovation Networks

ISA - Instituto Superior de Agronomia

EDIA – Empresa de Desenvolvimento e Infra-estruturas do Alqueva SA

CEF - Centro de Estudos Florestais

1. PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES

The preparatory activities included the anticipated alert/information of all Portuguese RAIN members about the meeting (date and place), using the emailing list managed by ISA. The emails were sent using a mailchimp account in order to keep track on the percentage of RAIN members reading the email (on average 50%). Due to the fact that the meeting occurred in 12th September, after August summer vacations typical in Portugal, a sequence of emails and social media alerts was planned in advanced. It included:

- First email alert ('Reserve now in your agenda') 2.5 months in advance, as soon has the date and place were settled (email send at 26/6/2018)
- Second email sent at the end of July, including a first program version.
- Third email alert including the final program at the first week of September

An event was also created in the Facebook group created and managed by ISA for the interaction of RAIN members: <https://www.facebook.com/events/620997481620081/> . This event was also used for live film and photo sharing, posterior materials dissemination and discussion among rain members.

The meeting was also publically announced on:

- CEF and ISA websites
- Event share and announcement in social media from RAIN members, institutions (CEF, EURAF, UNAC etc.)
- Press release sent to general social media contacts (ISA and CEF communication agents)

Preparatory activities also included contacting and inviting two farmers (members of the RAIN) and one researcher from University of Algarve. These contacts were fruitful and resulted in 3 successful presentations during the meeting. Regarding the selection of Herdade dos Lagos for the afternoon field trip included in the program, it implied a preparatory visit by ISA team to the farm.

2. AGENDA OF THE 3rd RAIN MEETING

Meeting description	
Brief description	3 rd Portuguese Regional Agroforestry Innovation Network (RAIN) meeting in Beja, Portugal
Date	12/09/2018
Time	9:00h - 13:00 14h30 - 16h30
Location	EDIA Beja, Portugal

Agenda	
9h00	Registration
9h30	Welcome José Salema (EDIA) Joana Paulo (ISA)
10h00	Presentation of the project' s final list of innovations João Palma (ISA)
10h30	9 european regions: differences and similarities among their agroforestry sectors. (Group discussion)
11h00	Coffe break
11h30	Carob cultivation and production Pedro Correia (Universidade do Algarve)
12h00	Herdade dos Lagos - An agrosilvopastural way to sustainability Helena Manuel (Herdade dos Lagos)

12h30	<u>Herdade da Abegoaria - The challenge of biodiversity</u> João Soares (Herdade da Abegoaria)
13h00	Lunch break
15h00	Field trip to Herdade dos Lagos, HDL.

3. LIST OF ATTENDEES

Table 1. List of attendees of the 3rd RAIN meeting in PORTUGAL

The signed list of attendees contains confidential information and it is not displayed.

The signed list of attendees was sent separately by email in a pdf file.

4. STAKEHOLDERS TAKING PART ON THE 3rd RAIN MEETING

Figure 1. Proportion of each stakeholder category in the 3rd RAIN meeting in Portugal

The majority of attendees were multipliers, followed by similar percentages of practitioners and researchers. New farmers and multipliers, living and working in the region of Beja and/or in the potential irrigation area of Alqueva, were invited to the meeting due to their specific and known interest in agroforestry.

A total of 26% of the meeting participants were practitioners. This is considered suitable according to the RAIN guidelines (33% of practitioners).

5. RESULTS OF THE 3rd RAIN MEETING

5.1. Validation list of innovations by stakeholders

The validation of the innovation list was made according to the following procedure:

1. Presentation of the full innovation list (without showing the country(ies) originating the innovation)
2. Game proposed to all participants, where they were asked to identify the countries that they thought were the 'responsible' for each the innovation
3. Each participant was asked the following question: 'what was/were the most important/interesting/surprising' innovation you saw in the list?
4. Discussion among all the participants

The list of innovations indicated as priority are presented in Table 2.

Problems/suggestions:

- Some RAIN members refereed the evidence of two groups of innovations: one identified has (supposing) originated from Northern/Central European countries *versus* a second one (supposing) originated from Southern countries. This aspect did not raise an agreement among all of the present members.
- Some multipliers focused the difficulty of finding suitable public supportive measures for implementing some of the innovations presented in the list, since according to their opinion existing supportive measures are still 'guided towards traditional agroforestry systems'. This raised the discussion around rules for project applications and their impacts on innovation. Some of the participants from the administration stated that the institution responsible for the projects evaluation is only following strict rules that are defined at the national and EU level.
- Another topic under discussion was the lack of applications to the PDR2020 measure dedicated to the implementation of new agroforestry measures in comparison to the forestation measure, and the large percentage of projects rejected in that measure. The reasons for the first issue, agreed by some of the farmers and multipliers present are: best conditions given to the forestation measure in terms annual compensation. Regarding the second issue (large percentage of projects rejected in the measure dedicated to the installation of new agroforestry systems) it was again unclear the motives that originate it.

Table 2: Priority innovations for Portugal

Main theme	Innovation cluster	Innovation topic	Innovation title	Innovation type
Technical/Economical/Communication/Policy and Administration	Please use the clusters given in D1.10, annex 4	Please use the topics given in D1.10, annex 4	Please use the titles given in D1.10, annex 4	Please use the types given in D1.10, annex 4
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Livestock management	Animal feeding	Nutritional value of shrubs in agroforestry systems	Animal feeding
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Livestock management	Farming systems	Estimation of the stocking rates based on animal and type of understory	Best practice/New tool
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Livestock management	Farming systems	Mob grazing in agroforestry systems (dairy cows)	New practice
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Lower story management	Forestry	Forest gardening (including permacultural practices and planting on forest area)	New practice
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Lower story management	Irrigation	Agroforestry in the corners of irrigation pivots: making the most out of space and increasing irrigation water usage.	New practice
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Lower story management	Lower story management	Managing the tree understory in agroforestry systems	Lower story management
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Lower story management	Lower story management	Technical information on the use of agroforestry to prevent forest fires	Lower story management
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Lower story management	Medicinal plants	Stinging nettle (<i>Urtica dioica</i> , (for fibres and	Medicinal plants

			vitamin C extracts) in between rows of alder (<i>Alnus incana</i>)	
TECHNICAL CHALLENGE	Lower story management	Soil	Usage of ramial chipped wood of eucalyptus globulus as a natural fertilizer	Soil
ECONOMICAL CHALLENGE		Recreation	Farm diversification: examples of succesful and diverse acivities on a farm to ensure a sustainable farm income: direct sales, well-being holiday, herder holiday, rent of cottages, small wetlands, diverse grazers, traditional breeds, local circular economy, local energy production, etc..	New services
COMMUNICATIO N CHALLENGE		Continuous learning	Booklet and Online Map of AF real case studies and online map	Continuous learning
COMMUNICATIO N CHALLENGE		Continuous learning	Learning by doing... and by sharing: networking, and open days at farms	New ways of organising things

5.2. Proposed AFINET synergy regions

The most referred and discussed innovations by the participants, in addition to the ones originated from Portugal, came from Spain and Finland. In addition, some reference to France (pollarding) and Italy (new technics for olive grooves management) were also made by some farmers.

It is important to notice that it is the IB believe that the results are related to the location/region took place, and the participants. Despite this fact, being aware of all of the project activities (contact to RAIN members, to farmers and multipliers for the last 1.5 years), it is possible to identify the most relevant topics for the **PT RAIN** by the

following **key words**: silvopastoral system, natural understory, permaculture, mob grazing, carrying capacity, soil organic matter, water management.

5.3. Knowledge transfer during the 3rd RAIN

Apart from the innovation list validation and discussion, the program of the meeting was dedicated to knowledge transfer and experience sharing. The core subject was the carob tree (growth, yield, fruit production) and the economic sector around it (price evolution, transformation, commercialization etc). This native crop was chosen due to its characteristics and potential for dry climate conditions of South Portugal, and its relevance for silvopastoral management systems in dry conditions (around 300 mm average precipitation).

Three guests made distinct presentations: two from farmers and one from a researcher:

- Pedro Correia, a researcher from Universidade do Algarve spoke on “Carob cultivation and production”, and focused on the commercial and production features, the challenges brought by the sector, explaining the species vegetative cycle and particularities, its edaphic requirements and adaptability to silvopastoral management
- Helena Manuel (from Herdade dos Lagos) presented “Herdade dos Lagos - an Agrosilvopastoral way to sustainability”. She mentioned the latest history of the farm, acquired 35 years ago by the current owners, emphasizing their attention to ecological sustainability and protection of biodiversity.
- João Soares (from Herdade da Abegoaria) described the challenges he faces while maintaining sustainability and biodiversity on his farms, and implementing environmentally friendly agricultural practices to improve or at least maintain soil characteristics, increase production, decrease fertilization, etc., all in his presentation “Herdade da Abegoaria – the challenge of biodiversity”.

After a lunch break there was a field trip to Herdade dos Lagos, in Mértola. The visit focused on the silvopastoral carob orchard, where several questions were raised about carob tree planting, management and production. The relevance of the 1000 sheep present in the farm was evidenced in weed control, removal of tree suckers sparing the need for expensive labour and fertilize the soil. Attendees were very interested on the technical aspects of carob harvest, namely the usage of mechanical harvesting. Helena Manuel explained that, although there was a mechanical harvest trial at the farm made in previous years, it was chosen not to pursuit it since this practice caused an abundance of trunk wounds. Carob is currently manually harvested after the vineyard using the same work force. The trip proceeded to a mixed stand of carob tree and stone pine, where the benefit of sheep grazing was also noticeable. Here the technical aspects and restrains of investment support measures were discussed.

6. CONCLUSIONS OF THE 3RD RAIN

At the end of the meeting the main conclusion regarding the validation of the innovation list is that PT RAIN members are mostly interested in the following topics:

1. Silvopastoral systems
2. Natural understory (management related to fire risk and potential as animal fodder potential)
3. Permaculture
4. Mob grazing practices
5. Carrying capacity limits to support tree regeneration
6. Increase of soil organic matter
7. Water management under climate change

At this point (still to be confirmed and complemented by other synergies) each topic will be developed by ISA or by other AIFNET partners in the following way:

- Topic 1 - Film by EURAF and FIN RAIN in collaboration to ISA; factsheet by ISA.
- Topic 2 - Short tutorial film by ISA
- Topics 4, 5 and 6 - translation of Agforward leaflets to Portuguese
- Topic 7 - Short tutorial film by ISA and factsheet

View [here a film](#) made on the 3rd Portuguese RAIN meeting (in Portuguese).

ANNEX I: list of attendees

The signed list of attendees was sent separately by email in a pdf file.